

Methodology Of Conducting And Organizing The Pisa Research

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Abstract: *The article describes the educational importance of using international assessment studies in the biological education system, the purpose of implementing biology PISA research tasks in secondary schools, and its role in the education system. Also, opinions on the development of students' knowledge of PISA tasks are presented. This is where studying the PISA program is important.*

Keywords — PISA, test, computer, standard, consortium, school, assessment, demand, organization, main results, level, questionnaire.

INTRODUCTION.

In international assessment studies, not all students are given the same test questions. Test questions used in PISA studies are usually designed to assess the effectiveness of a country's education system. Research questions are not intended for individual assessment of students. Therefore, it is not necessary to distribute the same set of sample questions to every student. Thus, the set of PISA test materials is distributed randomly among the students participating in the test.

The PISA 2015 study was conducted using a computer system. Computers and computer technology have become a part of our daily life. The tradition of conducting the PISA international assessment program on a computer is also well established in a positive sense.

In 2015, many countries that expressed their desire to participate in the PISA international assessment program conducted computer-based testing for the first time. Only in some countries that are not ready to conduct it on a computer, the tests were conducted in paper form.

How are countries selecting schools to participate in PISA studies? PISA uses strict technical standards to select schools that participate in the study. The selection process of schools is quality assured and depends on a decision-making process that confirms that the samples achieved and the corresponding response rates meet the established norms.

If any country's response rate falls below a specified threshold, it will be reported. Additional information about PISA results can be obtained from the official website of the OECD organization (www.oecd.org/pisa).

Below we can see that the IHTT organization did not take into account the national data reports of some countries in cases where they did not meet or did not meet the technical requirements of the PISA research consortium:

Austria. As noted in the PISA-2000 Technical Report (IHTT, 2002), students enrolled in joint school and vocational programs did not meet the requirements of the PISA-2000 assessment technical standards. Thus, the published PISA-2000 reports for Austria have been described as inaccurate

databases (IHTT 2001). Only this error was corrected in the PISA-2003 study.

The Netherlands. As noted in the PISA-2000 Technical Bulletin (IHTT, 2002), the response rate of schools in the Netherlands was considered insufficient for inclusion in the PISA-2000 database. Therefore, the Netherlands was excluded from studies related to PISA-2000.

Luxembourg. In order to improve compliance with economic standards and to better reflect the national characteristics of the school system, organizational and linguistic changes were made in the conditions of test tasks between PISA-2000 and PISA-2003. In PISA-2000, students in Luxembourg were given an assessment book in each student's chosen test language one week before the assessment.

However, familiarity with the language of assessment in practice was a significant barrier for a significant number of students in PISA-2000 in Luxembourg. In PISA-2003 and PISA-2006, therefore, students were given a bilingual assessment sheet. Students had the opportunity to choose the appropriate language for themselves before the assessment. This led to greater comparisons with monolingual countries and, as a result, fairer assessments of student performance in reading, math, science, and problem solving. As a result of this change in procedures, the assessment processes and assessment results for Luxembourg between PISA-2000 and PISA-2003 are not comparable. PISA-2003 and PISA-2006 are comparable because the assessment conditions have not been changed.

United States of America. As part of the PISA 2006 study, there was an error in the publication of the PISA survey questions in the US, which resulted in page numbering and misinterpretation of the reading literacy guides, as well as students reading the test questions. caused inconvenience in answering.

Research results Are the results of the PISA study open data? The results of PISA studies are available online. Previous results can be found at www.oecd.org/pisa in the "Main Results" column and all the results information in the "Data" column.

What do test score scores mean? PISA scores can be placed on specific scales developed within each subject designed to

indicate the general competencies tested by PISA. These scales are divided into two levels representing the PISA test questions in groups: Level 1 is from basic skills only to more complex and increases in difficulty at each level. When students' results are checked in the test, their results in reading (text comprehension), mathematics and natural sciences are placed on a suitable scale. For example, in the PISA test, a student who does not have the skills necessary to correctly complete the simplest questions will enter a level 1 class, but students should have these skills at a high level. For each subject, the participating country's score is the average score of all students in that country.

A student's score on each subject test from a country is the average of all students' scores from that country. The average score of the countries is 500 points and the standard deviation is 100 points. Approximately two-thirds of students from IHTT countries scored between 400 and 600 points.

How are participating countries ranked in the PISA rankings? PISA evaluates participating countries based on their performance in reading (comprehension of text), mathematics and science. PISA does not give an overall score for all subjects, instead it gives an assessment for each subject area and sets an average score for each area. However, it is not possible to assign a specific level to each country in each subject.

What steps are taken to ensure the reliability of PISA tests and results? PISA's belief in transparency is not only about the statistical model that evolves over time, but also about the rigor applied to all technical aspects of research design, implementation and analysis. In particular, in the development of tests, the reliability of assessments is related to the rigor of the procedures used in their development, criticism, analysis, review and selection.

For experts, this is to ensure that all aspects of the issue are taken into account and to provide an expert opinion in selecting a set of test materials that are sufficiently balanced for these aspects. In PISA, this work is carried out by assessment experts working with advisory groups made up of international experts. Participating countries and economists also play an important role in the process of selecting this material.

Can students lie in PISA? PISA is the most advanced international, high-quality and high-performance educational assessment program in the world, and therefore it is very important that PISA data is 100% accurate and valid.

To this end, IHTT applies very strict conditions at all levels to ensure that the student's skills, information and performance are accurately reflected and that no form of deception is used. This trust is strengthened by the agreement between the IHTT and the requirements of the terms of participation of each country. Article 4 of the Consensus requires countries to develop comprehensive technical standards for PISA, including monitoring the safety of test materials and the safe administration of assessments.

These requirements are further refined through the PISA Action Guide, the School Coordinators' Guide and the Test

Administration Guide. These manuals provide clear instructions for the safe receipt, storage, and safe administration of all test materials. No one other than approved project staff has access to PISA security information and restricted materials. There is a formal confidentiality policy for approved project staff. Why do not all members of the People's Republic of China participate in PISA? In recent years, the national ministry has been conducting tests to prepare the PISA program for fuller participation in several provinces of China. Shanghai has been participating in PISA-2009. Beijing and Jiangsu and Guangdong provinces participated in PISA-2015 research.

How did the PISA research lessons help the development of countries' education systems? In the 2012 IHTT survey of countries participating in PISA, the majority of respondents indicated that the education policies of high-ranking countries or developing systems had an effective impact on their performance.

Many more countries report that PISA has influenced the development of new components of their national or federal assessment strategies. In relation to curriculum development and standards, many countries have focused on the impact of the PISA system on: benchmarking national curricula against PISA standards and assessments; formation of national standards; their impact on the education system; Inclusion of PISA-like competences in educational programs; aimed at setting standards that meet national requirements.

Can PISA scores measure students' interpersonal skills? As part of the PISA-2015 study, the assessment of students' knowledge was carried out on the basis of a computer-based assessment system without the use of human resources. This, in turn, made it possible to consistently determine the abilities of students. In particular, the work of students in cooperation with different groups can be reliably compared.

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Take a test on a computer. In 2020, at least 71-72 students will be selected from at least 28 educational institutions where 15-year-olds are educated in the process of approving control-test materials to take the computer test. If the educational

institution has 71-72 students or less, according to the rules of the study, all of them will participate in the test.

In the course of the main research in 2021, at least 42 students from 15-year-old students will be selected in each of at least 150 schools, a total of at least 6300 students.

Pupils take a computer test for 120 minutes in the areas of mathematics, reading (level of understanding of the text), and natural sciences.

Survey of students. Conducting a survey of students allows to determine their attitude to education and life experiences. Questionnaires will be collected from students selected for the test after a 15-minute break after the test. 35 minutes will be allotted for the survey.

Conducting a questionnaire from the administration of the educational institution. The data collected as a result of the survey from the administration of the educational institution (TE) allows to determine the factors that determine the differences in the educational system of the countries participating in the research. Instructions for filling out the questionnaire are given in the information materials intended for the Coordinator of the educational institution.

Summary.

The main goal of the PISA study is to provide internationally comparable data on students' reasoning, with clear implications for education policy and systems. The process of thinking logically under the task and seeing the mechanism of biological processes should tend to improve through education; the various supporting factors of this thinking process in the context of the educational process must be clearly defined and depend on the indicators in the assessment; the content of the field used in the evaluation must be closely related to the subjects taught in regular high school; In order for the assessment to be predictive of creative achievement in school and life, PISA tasks must be similar to real-life activities in the student's daily life and in the classroom.

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